

Dose-response analysis of published data on arsenic and cancer

Christian Ritz

May 24 2023

In this note, data used by Ryan (2003) and Morales and Ryan (2005) will be re-analyzed using generalized linear and nonlinear dose-response models for counts. The data contain cancer cases, person-years, and arsenic concentration (in $\mu\text{g/L}$) per age group and village (in Taiwan). In this note analyses will not utilize the age groups. Note also that there is one arsenic concentration per village.

A novel aspect is the use of follow-up time in a nonlinear dose-response model for count data, in the same way as in an ordinary log-linear Poisson model.

Methods

For each arsenic concentration x_i , it was assumed that the corresponding number of cancer cases y_i follows a distribution for count data with mean μ_i , which was described by a parametric regression model. Specifically, the mean number of cases μ_i was described by the following four-parameter log-logistic model, which is an s-shaped model commonly used in toxicology (Ritz *et al.*, 2019):

$$\mu_i = \beta_2 + \frac{\beta_3 - \beta_2}{1 + \exp\{\beta_1(\log(x_i) - \log(\beta_4))\}} \quad (1)$$

The four parameters have the following interpretations: β_2 and β_3 correspond to the lower and upper limits on the mean number of cases at very small (close to 0) and very large arsenic concentrations. β_4 denotes the arsenic concentration (in $\mu\text{g/L}$) that results in a mean number halfway between the lower and upper limits (equal to $\beta_2 + (\beta_3 - \beta_2)/2$); this parameter is often referred to as *EC50* in toxicology. Finally, β_1 is the so-called slope parameter of the concentration-response curve at the arsenic concentration equal to β_4 . The slope parameter is a unitless quantity but can be scaled back to a proper slope coefficient using the this factor: $-(\beta_3 - \beta_2)/(4\beta_4)$.

The total observed follow-up time corresponding to the observed number of cancer cases y_i was denoted by z_i . Subsequently, the derived model for the incidence rate (IR_i) per 10000 person-years, corresponding to the arsenic concentration x_i , was obtained from the above model in Equation (1), through scaling by the total follow-up time z_i :

$$IR_i = \beta_2/z_i + \frac{\beta_3/z_i - \beta_2/z_i}{1 + \exp\{\beta_1(\log(x_i) - \log(\beta_4))\}} \quad (2)$$

implying that z_i became an offset in the model. The counts y_i could follow a Poisson distribution as would be common for cohort data (Morales and Ryan, 2005) or a negative-binomial distribution as proposed by Delignette-Muller *et al.* (2014) (in the context of ecotoxicology). In both cases maximum likelihood estimation could be applied.

In this note a Poisson distribution was assumed. The nonlinear concentration-response model in Equation (2) was fitted using the extension package *drc* for statistical environment **R** (Ritz *et al.*, 2019; R Core Team, 2021). The resulting four parameter estimates with corresponding 95% confidence intervals were reported. Data and model fits were plotted to enable a comparison. Subsequently, benchmark dose methodology (using inverse regression) was applied to obtain estimated benchmark concentration (BMC) values, corresponding

to increases in incidence rate of 1, 2, and 3 cancer cases per 10000 person-years, respectively (Jensen *et al.*, 2022).

Preparations

Information about R version

```
sessionInfo()

## R version 4.1.2 (2021-11-01)
## Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
## Running under: Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS
##
## Matrix products: default
## BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/blas/libblas.so.3.10.0
## LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/lapack/liblapack.so.3.10.0
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_CTYPE=da_DK.UTF-8      LC_NUMERIC=C
## [3] LC_TIME=da_DK.UTF-8      LC_COLLATE=da_DK.UTF-8
## [5] LC_MONETARY=da_DK.UTF-8  LC_MESSAGES=da_DK.UTF-8
## [7] LC_PAPER=da_DK.UTF-8    LC_NAME=C
## [9] LC_ADDRESS=C            LC_TELEPHONE=C
## [11] LC_MEASUREMENT=da_DK.UTF-8 LC_IDENTIFICATION=C
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods    base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] plyr_1.8.8      metafor_4.0-0      numDeriv_2016.8-1.1
## [4] metadat_1.2-0   drc_3.2-0          drcData_1.1-3
## [7] fitdistrplus_1.1-11 lmtest_0.9-40     zoo_1.8-12
## [10] sandwich_3.0-2  nlme_3.1-159      multcomp_1.4-20
## [13] TH.data_1.1-1   MASS_7.3-58.1     survival_3.4-0
## [16] mvtnorm_1.1-3   lme4_1.1-30       Matrix_1.5-1
## [19] ggplot2_3.4.0   rmarkdown_2.16
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] Rcpp_1.0.9      lattice_0.20-45    gtools_3.9.3      assertthat_0.2.1
## [5] digest_0.6.29   utf8_1.2.2        IRdisplay_1.1     R6_2.5.1
## [9] repr_1.1.4      evaluate_0.16     highr_0.9         pillar_1.8.1
## [13] rlang_1.1.0     uuid_1.1-0        minqa_1.2.4       car_3.1-0
## [17] nloptr_2.0.3    mathjaxr_1.6-0    labeling_0.4.2    splines_4.1.2
## [21] stringr_1.5.0   munsell_0.5.0     tinytex_0.41      compiler_4.1.2
## [25] xfun_0.33       pkgconfig_2.0.3   base64enc_0.1-3   htmltools_0.5.3
## [29] tidyselect_1.2.0 tibble_3.1.8      codetools_0.2-18  fansi_1.0.3
## [33] crayon_1.5.1    dplyr_1.0.10     withr_2.5.0       grid_4.1.2
## [37] jsonlite_1.8.0  gtable_0.3.1     lifecycle_1.0.3   DBI_1.1.3
## [41] magrittr_2.0.3  scales_1.2.1     carData_3.0-5     cli_3.6.0
## [45] stringi_1.7.8   farver_2.1.1     generics_0.1.3    vctrs_0.5.2
## [49] boot_1.3-28     IRkernel_1.3      tools_4.1.2       glue_1.6.2
## [53] plotrix_3.8-2   abind_1.4-5       fastmap_1.1.0     yaml_2.3.5
## [57] colorspace_2.0-3 pbdZMQ_0.3-7     knitr_1.40
```

Loading relevant packages

```
library(drc)
library(ggplot2)
library(plyr)
```

Data import

Data on bladder cancer among females are imported from the text file that is part of the zip file “arsenic.zip”, downloaded from the statlib datasets archive (<http://lib.stat.cmu.edu/datasets/>).

```
fblad <- read.table("/home/christian/stat/manuscripts/2023/arsenic-note/arsenic/fblad.sw.dat",
header = TRUE)
```

```
str(fblad)
```

```
## 'data.frame':  559 obs. of  5 variables:
## $ group  : int  1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ...
## $ conc   : int  0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 ...
## $ age    : num  22.5 27.5 32.5 37.5 42.5 47.5 52.5 57.5 62.5 67.5 ...
## $ at.risk: int  2595529 1846189 1402764 1215899 1191615 1111810 957985 774836 634758 492203 ...
## $ events : int  0 2 0 2 8 14 36 52 77 68 ...
```

```
head(fblad, 20)
```

```
##   group conc  age at.risk events
## 1     1    0 22.5 2595529      0
## 2     1    0 27.5 1846189      2
## 3     1    0 32.5 1402764      0
## 4     1    0 37.5 1215899      2
## 5     1    0 42.5 1191615      8
## 6     1    0 47.5 1111810     14
## 7     1    0 52.5  957985     36
## 8     1    0 57.5  774836     52
## 9     1    0 62.5  634758     77
## 10    1    0 67.5  492203     68
## 11    1    0 72.5  342767     70
## 12    1    0 77.5  199630     43
## 13    1    0 82.5   96293     21
## 14    2   10 22.5    934      0
## 15    2   10 27.5    489      0
## 16    2   10 32.5    276      0
## 17    2   10 37.5    317      0
## 18    2   10 42.5    374      0
## 19    2   10 47.5    435      1
## 20    2   10 52.5    342      0
```

Note that the variable group contains an enumeration of the villages.

Aggregating data

Aggregating data across age groups within sites:

```
fblad.agg <- ddply(fblad, .(conc),
function(dSet){c(unlist(dSet[1, c("group", "conc")]),
apply(dSet[, c("at.risk", "events")], 2, sum))})
```

Model fitting

Below models are fitted using the raw data. However, models fitted on aggregated data will lead to the same results, except for very small discrepancies due to the numerical estimation procedure.

Fitting a two-parameter log-linear Poisson model:

```
fblad.poisreg <- glm(events ~ conc + offset(log(at.risk/10000)), data = fblad,
family = poisson)
summary(fblad.poisreg)
```

```
##
## Call:
## glm(formula = events ~ conc + offset(log(at.risk/10000)), family = poisson,
##      data = fblad)
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -13.0376  -0.4295  -0.2379  -0.1352   11.7776
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept) -1.116432   0.048270  -23.13  <2e-16 ***
## conc         0.004366   0.000197   22.17  <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for poisson family taken to be 1)
##
##      Null deviance: 1759.3  on 558  degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance: 1529.3  on 557  degrees of freedom
## AIC: 1735.7
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 7
```

```
logLik(fblad.poisreg)
```

```
## 'log Lik.' -865.8731 (df=2)
```

```
AIC(fblad.poisreg)
```

```
## [1] 1735.746
```

Fitting a four-parameter log-logistic model in the model fitting function *drm()* in the **R** package *drc* (Ritz *et al.*, 2019):

```
fblad.LL.4 <- drm(events ~ conc, weights = at.risk/10000, data = fblad,
fct = LL.4(), type = "Poisson", start = c(-0.4, 1, 60, 10000))
summary(fblad.LL.4)
```

```
##
## Model fitted: Log-logistic (ED50 as parameter) (4 parms)
##
## Parameter estimates:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error t-value  p-value
## b:(Intercept) -3.6984e-01  1.1172e-01 -3.3104 0.0009317 ***
## c:(Intercept)  3.0580e-01  1.5428e-02 19.8212 < 2.2e-16 ***
```

```
## d:(Intercept) 4.1904e+01 4.8088e+01 0.8714 0.3835268
## e:(Intercept) 1.3377e+05 4.4336e+05 0.3017 0.7628708
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
logLik(fblad.LL.4)
```

```
## 'log Lik.' 1535.95 (df=555)
```

```
AIC(fblad.LL.4)
```

```
## [1] -1961.901
```

Note that the choice of starting values requires some trial and error.

Based on the AIC values the four-parameter log-logistic model provided a better fit than the two-parameter log-linear model.

Plotting data and fits

Defining the model functions to plot. In this case where weights were used for the estimation in *drm()*, *plot.drc()* in *drc* will not currently provide the right plot. Instead predicted values have to be calculated manually using the estimated parameters. For the log-linear Poisson model the *predict* can be used.

```
doseVal <- seq(0.1, 750, by = 0.5)
respVal1 <- predict(fblad.poisreg, data.frame(conc = doseVal, at.risk = 10000), type = "response")
respVal2 <- 0.31 + (41.9 - 0.31) / (1 + exp(-0.37*(log(doseVal) - log(133770))))
summary(respVal2)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 0.5338  3.6721  4.5544  4.3082  5.1611  5.6361
```

```
dr.data1 <- data.frame(x = fblad.agg[["conc"]],
  y = 10000*fblad.agg[["events"]] / fblad.agg[["at.risk"]])
dr.data2 <- data.frame(x = doseVal, y = respVal1)
dr.data3 <- data.frame(x = doseVal, y = respVal2)
```

For plotting aggregated raw data were used:

```
summary(dr.data1)
```

```
##           x           y
## Min.      : 0.00   Min.   : 0.000
## 1st Qu.: 61.25   1st Qu.: 0.000
## Median :283.00   Median : 2.337
## Mean     :321.24   Mean    : 3.865
## 3rd Qu.:535.75   3rd Qu.: 6.874
## Max.     :934.00   Max.    :16.779
```

Finally, the plot is produced using the function *ggplot()* from the package *ggplot2*:

```
dr.plot <- ggplot(dr.data1, aes(x = x)) + ylim(c(0, 20)) +
  xlab(expression(paste("Arsenic concentration (", mu, "g/L)"))) +
  ylab("Incidence rate (per 10000 person-years)") + theme_bw() +
  geom_point(aes(x = x, y = y), size = 2, pch = 21) +
  geom_line(data = dr.data2, aes(x = x, y = y), size = 1) +
  geom_line(data = dr.data3, aes(x = x, y = y), size = 1, color = "grey") +
  scale_x_continuous(trans = "log10") + coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0.1, 750), clip = "off")
```

```
dr.plot
```


Estimating BMC values

BMC values corresponding to an increase in incidence of 1, 2, and 3 per 10000 person-years (over the background incidence of 0.3 case per 10000 person-years) were estimated using the function $ED()$ in *drc*:

```
ED(fblad.LL.3, 3.0580e-01 + c(1, 2, 3), type = "absolute", interval = "delta", level = 0.90)
```

```
##
## Estimated effective doses
##
##           Estimate Std. Error   Lower   Upper
## e:1:1.3058    5.9866   23.7678  -33.1079  45.0812
## e:1:2.3058   41.7065  153.0577 -210.0510 293.4639
## e:1:3.3058  133.8026  471.5787 -641.8754 909.4805
```

From the output the resulting estimated BMC_1 , BMC_2 , and BMC_3 were 6, 42, and 134 $\mu\text{g/L}$. BMCL could not be obtained due to the negative lower limits of the 90% confidence intervals, indicating that there was not sufficient information in the data to fully support the four-parameter log-logistic model.

References

- Delignette-Muller, M. L., Lopes, C., Veber, P., Charles, S. (2014). Statistical handling of reproduction data for exposure-response modeling. *Environmental Science & Technology*, **48**, 7544–51. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es502009r>
- Jensen, S. M., Kluxen, F. M., Ritz, C. (2022). Benchmark dose modelling in regulatory ecotoxicology, a potential tool in pest management. *Pest Management Science*, **78**, 1772–1779. <http://doi.org/10.1002/ps.6759>
- Morales, K.H. and Ryan, L.M. (2005), Benchmark dose estimation based on epidemiologic cohort data. *Environmetrics*, **16**, 435–447. <https://doi.org/10.1002/env.713>
- R Core Team, 2021. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Ritz, C., Jensen, S. M., Gerhard, D., Streibig, J. C. (2019). Dose-Response Analysis Using R. Boca Raton: CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b21966>
- Ryan, L. (2003). Epidemiologically Based Environmental Risk Assessment. *Statistical Science*, **18**, 466–480. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3182836>